

Branding equity: the application and ethics of evolutionary psychology in marketing

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Abstract

Emotions inform behavior, and when companies are adept at manipulating our emotional responses, marketing and advertising can be utilized to influence our decisions about what products to buy. Evolutionary psychology currently provides the strongest explanation for how humans process information. Using an evolutionary psychology model to predict emotional reactions in consumers is revolutionizing how marketing companies are promoting their products. The ability to manipulate people's emotional states by using more accurate models of human information-processing systems begs ethical questions regarding responsibility in marketing. After an examination of the application of evolutionary psychology to marketing, the ethics involved in applying these ideas to the marketplace will be discussed.

Keywords: Evolutionary Psychology, evolution, marketing, ethics

Emotions are the translation of perceptual information into incitements to behavior. Emotions act as heuristics designed to solve recurring problems in our environments. They facilitate our successful navigation through social environments by providing cues and inferences about particular situations. Our sociality as a species has initiated selective pressures to refine a complex set of emotional directives that afford humans the possibility to discern and infer information that is useful in social settings. These emotional heuristics have been selected throughout our evolutionary history to equip us with the resources to increase our probability of survival and reproduction.

Knowledge of emotional attachment has been used repeatedly by companies attempting to influence consumer's purchasing behavior. Following guidelines congruent with the biological architecture of emotional behavior, many marketing campaigns are designed to access our emotional mechanisms of motivation in order to promote their products. Emotions inform behavior, and when companies are adept at manipulating our emotional responses, marketing and advertising can be utilized to influence our decisions about what products to buy. In addition to traditional marketing and advertising techniques, contemporary perspectives and novel research in evolutionary psychology is leading to increasingly nuanced renditions of advertising that are sensitive to a wide array of variables that were not readily explainable with previous models of human psychology. Evolutionary psychology is currently discovering gender differences, developmental trajectories, and coalition-formation facts that are updating our understanding of how humans process information. Utilizing these findings for the purpose of influencing purchase behavior is likely to transform the relationship between marketing and psychology.

Evolutionary psychology currently provides the strongest explanation for how humans process information. Using this model to predict emotional reactions in consumers is revolutionizing how marketing companies are promoting their products. The ability to manipulate people's emotional states by using more accurate models of human information-processing systems begs ethical questions regarding responsibility in marketing. After an examination of the application of evolutionary psychology to

marketing, the ethics involved in applying these ideas to the marketplace will be discussed.

Evolutionary Psychology – What is it?

Evolutionary based perspectives of behavior focus predominantly upon psychological and biological mechanisms that were “designed” by evolution to help organisms successfully genetically replicate. Psychological mechanisms and the associated behaviors that helped our ancestors survive and reproduce were passed along to subsequent generations by means of genetic replication.

Evolutionary psychology seeks to explain why certain cognitions, emotions and behaviors exist, and what situations existed in our ancestral history that gave rise to these thoughts, feelings and behaviors. Darwin (1871/1981) espoused the theory of natural selection in which he professed that organisms that more successfully adapt to environments due to random mutations will more likely survive and reproduce. That is, we are directly descended from organisms that were better at solving the problems faced in our evolutionary history. Steven Pinker (1997, p. 21) states that one of the pivotal tenets of evolutionary psychology is that, “the mind is a system of organs of computation, designed by natural selection to solve the kinds of problems our ancestors faced in their foraging way of life, in particular, understanding and outmaneuvering animals, plants, and other people.” The purpose of these organs of computation is to maximize the inclusive fitness of the organism.

Darwin (1871/1981) utilized individual reproductive success as the barometer of fitness in his theory of natural selection. This meant that the basic denominator for evaluating whether a behavior was to be selected for was its impact on the individual organism’s reproductive success. The theory of inclusive fitness, however, interprets fitness in terms of genetic continuation, assessing the likelihood of genes being replicated over successive generations. From this perspective, individual reproduction may not be the sole determinant of selection, for relatives that share genetic similarities must also be factored

into the cost and benefit equation of survival and continuation. That is, selection is understood in terms of the continuation of genes, which we share with our relatives, and not in terms of ultimate benefit to the individual. In a framing that was popularized in his book *The Selfish Gene*, Richard Dawkins (1989, 1999) described the individual organism as a mere “vehicle” for genetic continuation. Genes are the yardstick by which natural selection is measured. The theory of genetic selection in evolutionary psychology “offers the best explanation of the conditions under which genetic structures and the behaviors they give rise to benefit and become widespread as the result of social transactions” (Burnstein, Crandall, & Kitayama, 1994, p. 774).

In Tooby and Cosmides’ (1990, p. 417) view, “the mind consists primarily of a collection of evolved function-specific information processing mechanisms with such views as that emotions are coordinated systems that organize action appropriate to situations.” Emotions, like cognitive mechanisms, evolved in ways that have benefited the organism (in terms of survival and reproduction) in ancestral environments. Emotions regulate behavior by providing “an integrated mode of operation that functions as a solution designed to take advantage of the particular structure of the recurrent situation these emotions correspond to” (Tooby & Cosmides, 1990, pg. 410). For example, the emotion of fear is designed to assist an organism to free itself from threatening situations. Increased visual and auditory awareness, adrenaline, and increased blood flow are initiated when fear is present in order to protect the organism from threat. Over repeated exposures in our evolutionary history to predatory threat and physical injury, organisms that evolved the capacity for initiating the emotion of fear, and its concomitant behaviors, were selected for because of their increased advantage for survival. The environment triggers an emotional reaction that provides a solution to the evolutionary problem (in the case of fear, the avoidance of physical injury or death).

Various emotions provide different solutions to different evolutionary problems. Emotions prepare the organism for behavioral response. Certain emotions trigger the mechanics of an organism to prepare for responses that have proven successful over evolutionary time. Our emotional states are a result of our biological development and

social learning. The theory espoused by Cosmides and Tooby (2000), and the examples provided by evolutionary research in other species (Killen & de Waal, 2000), purport that emotions (as well as cognitive mechanisms) have evolved to facilitate responses that ultimately benefit that organism's genetic survival.

In order for the genetic structures and evolved psychological mechanisms to become widespread, the mechanisms must have pertinently addressed adaptive problems in our evolutionary history. Evolved motivational systems direct our behavior in ways that maximized our fitness in ancestral environments. Basically, emotions guided us to what we should eat, with whom we should mate, and how we may best socially relate. By activating these cognitive and emotional programs that have been evolved in humans, marketing campaigns may elicit desired behaviors from potential consumers and alter purchasing behaviors.

Emotions, Evolutionary Psychology and Their Relationship to Marketing

Emotions perform an adaptive function by initiating motivation for behaviors that repeatedly maximized fitness in ancestral environments. In the field of marketing research, understanding and manipulating consumer emotions provides a possibility to influence purchasing behavior. Kleinginna and Kleinginna (1981, p.371) claim that,

Emotion is a complex set of interactions among subjective and objective factors, mediated by neuronal/hormonal systems, which (a) give rise to affective experiences such as feelings of arousal, pleasure/displeasure; (b) generate cognitive processes such as emotionally relevant perceptual effects, appraisals, labeling processes; (c) activate widespread physiological adjustments to the arousing conditions; and (d) lead to behavior that is often, but not always, expressive, goal-directed, and adaptive.

Marketers that are able to induce this emotionally goal-directed behavior in consumers may better influence purchasing behavior. By aligning marketing campaigns with the adaptive features of our emotional architecture, marketers and advertisers may more effectively influence consumer behavior. The more accurate understanding marketing

companies have of human nature, the more they may tailor advertising campaigns to activate the emotional systems that will lead to the consumption of their products. Evolved human preferences may be used to steer human's thoughts and emotions in ways that lead to greater brand recognition, better brand evaluation and brand consumption.

Consumption is a bio-social phenomenon that is a product of our evolved psychological architecture (Colarelli & Dettman, 2003; Sherry, 1991). Current theories in marketing psychology have not fully anticipated the explanatory power of evolutionary psychology and its promise as a tool for marketing research and analysis. As Jackson (2002, p. 296) notes, "the utility calculus on which consumer behavior is based in the economic model is a crude and ill-formed model of human nature when compared with the multiplicity of behaviors and complexity of proximal motivations highlighted by evolutionary psychology." Much of our behavior as economic consumers springs from our biological nature and our evolved motivation to maximize our fitness. This means that we are continually attempting to promote ourselves sexually and socially and that our decisions as consumers will reflect this proclivity.

Rational decision making is only rational to the extent that it is adaptive and promotes inclusive fitness (Saad & Gill, 2000). Humans use cost-benefit analyses to arrive at decisions that benefit them in terms of survival and reproduction (Gigerenzer & Goldstein, 1996). Social role theory does not adequately explain behaviors because it is imprecise about the causes that underlie variations in decision-making across cultures and gender (Barkow, Cosmides, Tooby, 1991; Buss, 1996, 1999; Saad & Gill, 2000). Therefore, as we look to the applications of evolutionary psychology to marketing, we will find it most accurately represents the architecture of the human mind and therefore offers one of the strongest models for understanding and influencing consumer behavior.

Applications of Evolutionary Psychology to Marketing

Marketers and advertisers have long used intuitive psychology to sell products to consumers. However, with greater explanations offered by a scientific theory, these

intuitive psychologies may be honed to better access the emotional programs that influence purchasing behavior. For example, creating “cute” facial features in mascots and stuffed toys that parallel the neotenous features (large head size relative to body, large eyes, small nose) of human infants initiates emotional responses (Tinbergen, 1951). These perceptual cues engender feelings of cuteness and sentiments of care-taking that have been used by companies, such as Disney and Hallmark, to sell products (Cary, 2000). Orians & Heerwagen (1992) claim that consumer preferences for savanna like landscapes are influenced by our evolutionary history and a wide variety of companies use back grounds and panoramas that mimic our ideal ancestral environments (Saad & Gill, 2000). The Axe brand marketing campaign using provocatively dressed women plays on a number of sexually selected mechanisms that are predicated by evolutionary theory (Symons, 1979). Narrow-casting and blog sites that marketers use to generate discussion about their products are similarly based on human communication and social influences that may be honed by a greater understanding of evolved social mechanisms (Dunbar, 1996). Finally, the psychological mechanisms that predispose people to imitate socially high-ranking and attractive individuals has led to a plethora of marketing campaigns designed to have consumers imitate actors and spokespersons endorsing a given product (Bandura, 1991; Colerelli & Dettman, 2003). This advertising strategy works because mimicking the behavior of high status individuals was useful in ancestral environmental. Imitating high-status and competent exemplars allowed individuals to efficiently identify and utilize adaptive skills, values and beliefs (Henrich & Gil-White, 2001).

The reasons that these strategies for marketing consumer goods are efficient may be best explained by using a model of evolutionary psychology. Furthermore, a clear understanding of this theoretical perspective will increase a company’s ability to more efficiently design marketing strategies that tap these emotional programs. Specifically, we will look at gender influences and group dynamics as examples of how evolutionary psychology may be more efficiently applied to marketing research and design.

Gender differences

George Williams (1966) suggests that gender disparities exist due to the different sacrifices necessary for men and women to achieve reproduction. The differences in potential parental investment lead to varying strategies in mate selection between men and women. Females tend to be more discriminatory because their potential minimum investment is much higher compared to males. Males, in turn, exhibit more agentic and promiscuous behaviors (Archer, 1996; Symons, 1979). These fundamental dispositions toward procreation also influence purchasing behavior.

Males, in competition for females that are naturally more selective, attempt to display themselves as worthy mates. They do so by flaunting resources and signs of success and by engaging in intra-sexual competition. Therefore, males will tend to accumulate material goods that exhibit their social positions in order to indicate to females that they have adequate resources to be a good potential suitor (Jackson, 2002). Males are also more likely to engage in risk taking behavior, be it physical or financial (Saad & Gill, 2000). Catering to the purchase behavior of males may include marketing aimed at winning males over in spontaneous decisions based upon perception of increasing status position. Males also tend to have a more short term mating strategy than women, and visual stimulus of the opposite sex generally excites males more than it does females. In turn, a surfeit of advertisements employs undressed women to capture males' attention and to create positive associations for their products (Colerelli & Dettman, 2003).

Women, on the contrary, do not react as positively to opposite sex nudity (Saad, 2004). Women are, however, concerned with their value as potential mates. Unlike males, whose primary design is to indicate resource acquisition as cues to industriousness and ambition, females tend to display youth and attractiveness as key features when attempting to procure mates (Saad & Gill, 2000; Symons, 1979). This transpires with enormous resonance in the cosmetic and beauty industry. Men have a sexual affinity for youth because our ancestors that had this affinity bore more children than those that mated with women with curtailed fertility windows. In turn, men place greater emphasis on women's physical attractiveness as an indicator of youth and fertility and women respond by ardently attempting to portray themselves as young and fertile. The beauty industry

thrives off of this predisposition, selling 93% of cosmetics products to women (Colarelli & Dettman, 2003). Slowing the aging process, enhancing the beauty of one's hair and body parts are all facets of creating the appearance of youth and fertility. Full lips, unblemished skin and a waist-to-hip ratio of approximate 0.7 are all physical indicators that we have evolved to perceive as "beautiful" because they are telltale signs of youth and fertility (Buss, 1996; Singh, 1993). The beauty industry has capitalized on women's desire to appear as such, and has created campaigns promising changes that will bring male suitors. A 1928 advertisement for Palmolive soap captures this sentiment concisely in the caption that accompanies a picture of a young female with flowers: "He remembered that schoolgirl complexion. Youth is charm, and youth lost is charm lost, as every woman instinctively realizes" (Goodrum & Dalrymple, 1990, p.130).

References to physical appearance will intuitively resonate more with women. This can be widely used by marketers to capture female attention and impress upon them emotional points. Campaigns against smoking, for example, may engage women's emotional response by indicating that smoking causing wrinkles and damages hair and skin. Part of the allure of smoking for men, on the other hand, may have been the marketing designed to exemplify it as a somewhat risky and macho behavior, as portrayed by cowboys in advertisements and throw-caution-to-the-wind lead male roles in movies.

Women's menstrual cycles also influence their perceptions and potentially their purchasing behavior. Women's preferences for men alternate throughout their monthly cycle, with women preferring men exhibiting high testosterone markers (pronounced chin, wide jaw line, prominent brow ridge) when they are close to ovulation (Gangestad, 1998). This piece of information is readily explainable by sexual selection mechanisms in evolutionary psychology and has been found to influence women's choices regarding socializing and fashion (Gangestad et al., 2004). Saad and Gill (2000) report that women near ovulation dress more provocatively at singles bar and wear more make-up and jewelry than at other times during their menstrual cycle. This has potential implications for marketers of lingerie and cosmetics to target female consumers at specific intervals in

their menstrual cycle. Because mating strategies alternate for women during their cycle, marketers may attend to both the variations in female menstration as well as the differences evolved between genders.

The differences in gender mating strategies also lead to variations in gift giving tactics. Saad & Gill (2003) claim that while males and females did not differ in the amount of money spent on their romantic partners, their motivations for gift giving were different. While women purchased gifts in order to celebrate the relationship, men were more likely to use gifts “as a means of ‘displaying long-term interest’ early in the relationship” (Saad & Gill, 2003, p.779). Men, more frequently than women, have tactical or goal-oriented motives for gift-giving. Saad and Gill (2003) mention three primary motives for males engaging in gift-giving: (a) to flaunt resources, (b) to display their generosity, or (c) as a prelude to seduction. According to Saad and Gill (2003), females operate less frequently along these strategic lines of gift-giving, although they are able to discern more accurately the strategic intentions behind gift giving.

While this leads to a complex interaction between the genders, marketers that heed the advances of the psychological sciences will be able to better tap the evolved emotional reactions of individuals. Often, our reactions not only come from our individualized responses to suggestion, but follow a social order that marketers are likewise able to utilize. Group dynamics afford a means of introducing and advantageously placing consumer products in a favorable light.

Group dynamics

In his paper on advertising to the groups of people, Earls (2003) advocates that humans do not operate as individual entities. Rather, Earls asserts that we are evolved to function socially with proclivities toward communal interaction and social hierarchy. He emphasizes a “herd” mentality that takes account of emotions in a non-individual way. This view is echoed by Ostergard & Jantzen (2000, p.11) when they suggest that the “consuming individual is a member of a tribe, where the product symbolism creates a

universe for the tribe.” In accordance with this conception, Earls (2003) reinforces the hypothesis that the social nature of humans influences our decisions and consumer behavior. When other members of the group acknowledge, discuss and make decisions about products, we will naturally be influenced by them. Therefore, companies that pay attention to the social dynamics of groups stand to benefit from the collective and social influences that consumers are subject to.

Many theorists have outlined the importance of social influences on behavior acquisition and cognition (Bandura, 1991; Dunbar, 1996; Wertsch, 1985). Earls (2003) states that rules are followed because of social pressures and are therefore upheld and influenced by the group. This applies directly to rules about consumerism as well, and highlights the importance of social endorsement of products. One of the most common ways to achieve reliable information about a product is by word of mouth.

Recent studies (Kamins, Folkes and Perner, 1997) suggest that word-of-mouth reports account for more than 80% of the influence on people’s purchasing behavior. Dunbar (1996) has provided evidence for the evolutionary benefits of verbal information sharing and his work clarifies the underlying social mechanisms functioning in marketing and advertising. Social networks provide humans with important and relevant information, and marketers and advertisers that are able to successfully input product information into the social verbal exchange will have significant advantage in the marketplace. As Gladwell (2001, p.14) reflects,

Advertisers spent the better part of the 20th century trying to control and measure and manipulate the spread of information – to count the number of eyes and ears that they could reach with a single message. But...the most successful ideas are those that spread and grow because of the customer’s relationship with other customers – not the marketer’s to the customer.

Earls (2003) highlights the importance of creative marketing strategies within the context of the social relating of information. Given the evidence afforded to us by evolutionary psychology, information that is novel and important to our well-being will be proliferated

through the social sphere (Dunbar, 1996). Krishnan (1996) identifies “unique associations” as one facet of successful high equity brands. This hypothesis is congruent with literature in cognitive psychology and memory studies that suggest that subjects’ recognition performance is higher for novel information (Habib, McIntosh, Wheeler, Tulving, 2003). Additionally, marketing campaigns that focus on information that is socially beneficial to share provide one way to achieve brand recognition using social dynamics. This means that advertisements that capture pertinent social information are most likely to be shared by many. This is usually achieved by suggesting that a product or service will dramatically improve one’s life, or one’s family and friend’s lives. Having people attest to these claims, as is often done in infomercials, begins a process of information sharing that in ancestral environments was used for survival and reproduction, but is here employed to sell goods and services. This is similarly why news and documentary style advertisements have been successful in marketing campaigns ranging from book sales to political agendas. The formality and urgency of fake news specials heightens our attention and alerts us to upcoming information that may potentially benefit us.

Having high-status individuals endorse products is also a strategy that utilizes social dynamics. Bandura (1986) and Milgram (1974) have illustrated the social power of individuals. As stated above, high-status, attractive, and competent individuals have been, throughout our evolutionary history, great examples to follow. Today, advertisements use attractiveness, popularity and professional expertise to sell products. There is evidence in the marketing literature to suggest that brand equity may be maintained or improved by coupling specific celebrities with specific brands in order to foster beneficial secondary associations (Erdem & Swait, 1998; Krishnan, 1996). From a psychological perspective, information that comes from sources considered to be reputable is more likely to be acted upon and shared because this behavior was adaptive throughout our evolutionary history. This is reinforced by Earls (2003) notion that social networks may be harnessed by marketers and advertisers to contribute to individual consumer behavior by (a) understanding the roles social networks play, (b) finding out how networks work and (c) finding out how the network may be influenced.

One method of influence has been to identify pivotal individuals that act as the social connectors for the group. These are the well-networked people whose friends would call them on a weekend night to find out where all of their other friends and acquaintances are planning to meet. These “hubs” have been sought as the entrance point to information sharing and companies that continue social network research to identify these individuals will likely have a head-start on introducing and proliferating their products or services through social circles. One example of this is Abercrombie & Fitch’s marketing campaign to identify and offer free samples of clothing to prom kings and queens at American high schools. This promotional idea fits nicely within the theoretical literature pertaining to social influence. Prom kings and queens usually are popular and attractive, providing two criteria for the probable emulation of their behavior. Receiving free clothing would likely persuade these popular high school students to extol the virtues of the brand, introducing a third vector of social influence into the computation.

Social networks influence individual consumer decisions. We are programmed evolutionarily to heed the actions of successful and high-status individuals as well as listen to pertinent and socially shared information. Word-of-mouth associations feature as an integral component of brand equity and have been utilized to gauge the level of equity in consumer brands (Krishnan, 1996). Marketers that intentionally use these strategies may introduce information about their products into the social network and then prosper by having this information shared by word-of-mouth.

Many advertisers are using web-logs and chat rooms to mention their products and give favorable opinions of their companies. This phenomenon usually transpires without the employee of the company revealing their identification with the product or service. Companies are therefore attempting to influence social networks by deceptively pretending to be an engaged and discriminating consumer that has pertinent social information to share. Along with a number of other practices, this method of product promotion raises ethical considerations that deserve discussion.

Ethics and Evolutionary Psychology in Marketing

Is it ethical to manipulate consumer's emotional states without their consent or awareness? Are marketers intruding on people's emotional states by employing advertisements that are designed to anticipate consumer's reactions and persuade them to buy their companies goods and services? Evolutionary psychology offers a powerful means of understanding human psychology and provides a tool to design advertisements that play on the evolved emotional states of individuals and groups. Cary (2000, p. 104) recognizes that consumers themselves are not necessarily aware of the influence that marketing may be having on them because "evolution does not appear to have selected people for a knowledge of its own working." By "hijacking" our evolved mechanisms, marketers and advertisers may lead people to consume products that they do not need, purchase services that will not enhance their well-being and imbibe products that could be potentially harmful (Colarelli & Dettman, 2003). Marketing that plays on our evolved mechanisms may therefore be understood to be essentially deceptive. This may especially be the case when marketing campaigns promise results that do not logically follow directly from the purchase of the product and when marketing practices are not explicitly revealed to the consumer.

In January of this year, the Federal Trade Commission in the United States discussed with Proctor & Gamble Co. the need for salespersons to disclose their affiliation with the product in word-of-mouth marketing practices (Berner, 2006). The Word of Mouth Marketing Association (WOMMA), which mandates full disclosure, says Proctor and Gamble's new word-of-mouth marketing program, VocalPoint, raises ethical issues by not compelling their army of word-of-mouth advertisers to disclose their connections to the company. Proctor & Gamble advocates that it is up to the individual word-of-mouth sales team members to make this decision on their own. The question for business ethicists is whether non-disclosure is tantamount to consumer deception in advertising practices, or whether it is beyond the jurisdiction of business ethics and should be regarded as social information relayed between friends, family members and acquaintances.

Marketing companies' exploitation of peoples' innate psychology may also include advantageously positioning advertisements in places where they are more likely to resonate with consumers. For example, selective advertisements or coupons aimed for distribution with birth control purchases may take advantage of certain hormonal, emotional and psychological dispositions of women in given stages of ovulation. It will become an ethical agenda to illuminate whether or not this constitutes a witting manipulation of peoples' naturally fluctuating psychology in order to part them with their money or whether it provides an efficient outlet for marketers to advertise the products consumers want to buy. Would coupons and advertisements for Godiva chocolate or Haagen Dazs ice cream, issued specifically when a consumer is known to be in a melancholy mood, be regarded as taking advantage of the emotional state of the consumer (because they might not make the purchase under an alternative emotional disposition) or would it be considered a practical means of addressing consumer need in a functioning capitalistic economy?

Miller's (2000) position is congruent with the perspective that contemporary marketing practices place control in the hands of the consumer. Miller proposes that marketing has shifted the power from institutions to individuals. He claims that while technology originally put humans in the servitude of production, marketing has returned the authority to the people by asking what it is that consumers most want. However, getting exactly what we want has its own complications. We evolved in environments that were not as abundant in food stores and potential mates as many of the countries in the world today. In modern economies, "marketing threatens to put infinite production ability in the service of infinite human lust, gluttony, sloth, wrath, and vanity" (Miller, 2000, p.123).

Our emotional systems are designed to feel happy when are goals are being met. That is, human emotional systems were designed to experience a sense of happiness when individuals found themselves in situations that led to their survival or increased enhancement. Subsequently, the goal of much of marketing has been to make people believe that they are benefiting from a product or service and to make that person feel (or

believe they are) happy. Happiness research concludes that the promises that advertisements make about being able to increase our subjective well-being are mostly empty (Miller, 2006). Miller (2006, p.3) reports that, “people may act as if they are trying to increase their happiness by buying products, but they are not actually achieving that aim.” Does the grand illusion of fulfillment of desire, and the unawareness of the consumer, designate marketing practices unethical when they play on these variables?

Colarelli & Dettman (2003) acknowledge the ubiquity of deception in marketing but recognize deceit as an inherent attribute of human psychology and communication. Saad (2004) similarly takes account of some of the questionable practices of marketing by recognizing that marketers are simply taking advantage of the reality of evolved human emotional mechanisms. For these authors, it is simply the way that the human mind is structured that affords us the possibility to manipulate it intentionally. It is likewise the evolved mechanisms of marketers that incite them to do so in the first place. It is unlikely that marketing firms and advertising agencies will abstain from practices that use scientific theory to increase consumer response and interest. Perhaps the most reasonable answer is not to suggest that we discontinue application of evolutionary psychology in marketing, but that we provide, as Miller (2006, p.3) suggests, a warning label on all non-essential goods that reads: “Caution: scientific research demonstrates that this product will increase your subjective well-being only in the short term, if at all, and will not increase your happiness set-point.”

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